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Legal disclaimer

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Executive summary

Selkie (2019-2022) is a collaborative marine energy research and development project funded by the European Union's Ireland-Wales Cooperation Programme. Its aim is to develop a set of multi-use tools, templates, standards, and models in key shared technology areas. These tools will be developed in partnership with, and for the benefit of, marine energy industry stakeholders and will be made available, open-source, upon the conclusion of the project.

The present report constitutes the first deliverable (D5.1) in work package 5 of the Selkie project, which focuses on foundation and mooring system design. Beginning with an overview of the available technologies and design approaches, the report reviews existing tools for foundation, anchor, and mooring system design with a particular focus on open-source software tools and their applicability to marine energy projects. Its findings will be used to inform the research undertaken in work package 5 and the development of the corresponding Selkie design tool.

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1. Introduction

To achieve its objective of producing net-zero greenhouse gas emissions, the European Union has planned to completely decarbonise its energy supply by 2050 (European Commission, 2019). This ambitious task will require a diverse portfolio of renewable energy systems to make use not only of Europe's solar, onshore wind, hydropower, and bioenergy resources, but also the vast energy resources available offshore. Complementing that produced by the more established offshore wind energy industry, power generated from ocean waves and tidal currents has the potential to contribute significantly towards this green energy mix (Edenhofer et al., 2011; Magagna & Uihlein, 2015; Villate et al., 2020).

In recent years, there have been many technological breakthroughs in the tidal stream energy industry: following several successful demonstration projects, the first tidal turbine arrays are now powering Scottish homes and businesses; skills and infrastructure from the shipbuilding, fishing, and offshore oil and gas industries are being repurposed for application to tidal stream energy; and a UK-based export market is beginning to develop (Cagney & Gruet, 2019; Marine Energy Council, 2019). Though at an earlier stage of development, industrial clusters for wave energy are also beginning to emerge: many new prototypes are being designed, tested, and deployed, and the more incremental approach recently adopted by the industry means that although fewer wave energy devices will reach the full-scale deployment phase, those that do are more likely to be commercially viable (Cagney & Gruet, 2019).

Despite this progress, however, the widespread deployment of marine energy devices remains complicated, not only by the potential social and environmental impacts but also by numerous institutional, legal, technological, and economic barriers. Amongst the most pressing challenges faced by the marine energy industries at present are the lack of common components and procedures between devices, the lack of explicit knowledge sharing between technology developers often observed in growth industries, and the high costs associated with both research and development and pilot demonstration projects (Bonar et al., 2015; Magagna & Uihlein, 2015; Simas et al., 2015; Borthwick, 2016; European Commission, 2017; Copping & Hemery, 2020; IRENA, 2020).

As with other forms of renewable energy, the capital expenditure for wave and tidal stream energy is higher than for fossil fuel generation and, as with all offshore infrastructure, operations and maintenance costs are also high relative to the levelised cost of energy (LCOE) (Astariz & Iglesias, 2015; Uihlein & Magagna, 2016). To enable marine renewable energy projects to compete with other forms of electricity generation, technology and project developers must strive to reduce the LCOE by increasing their power output whilst also reducing their capital and operational expenditures (Astariz & Iglesias, 2015; Borthwick, 2016; Uihlein & Magagna, 2016). With a combined capacity of 2.9GW (or 1.5GW) installed by 2030, it is estimated that LCOE of €110/MWh (or €150/MWh) and €90/MWh (or €100/MWh) can be achieved for wave and tidal stream energy, respectively (Ocean Energy Europe, 2020). These cost reductions will be facilitated by the transfer of knowledge from the offshore wind energy sector, which achieved an average LCOE of €95/MWh in 2019 as the combined generating capacity of offshore wind turbines approached 50GW (Roser, 2020).

The foundation or mooring system is a key component of any marine renewable energy project, not only because it keeps the device on station and secured against extreme and often complex environmental loads but because it can also influence power production, particularly for floating systems where the efficiency of the energy extraction depends on the motion of the device (Harris et al., 2006; Paredes et al., 2013; Karimirad et al., 2014; Weller et al., 2015a; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Xu et al., 2019). Foundations and moorings also represent a large proportion of the total cost for a

marine energy project: mooring and anchoring costs are often quoted as representing 10-30% of the installed costs for marine energy devices, as compared to 2-3% for floating oil and gas facilities (Paredes et al., 2013; Karimirad et al., 2014; Knappett et al., 2015). This, coupled with the fact that array developments will require efficient and reliable systems to be produced in large numbers, makes the design of such systems crucial to the success of the project (Byrne & Houlsby, 2003; Harris et al., 2006; Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Paredes et al., 2013).

Owing to limited operational experience, the marine renewable energy industries have adopted a cautious approach and used, as the basis for their designs, methods and guidelines developed primarily for the offshore oil and gas industries (Harris et al., 2006; Paredes et al., 2013; Karimirad et al., 2014; Weller et al., 2015a). Though a sensible starting point for pilot projects, the scales, risks, and economics of marine energy are very different to those of offshore oil and gas extraction (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Paredes et al., 2013; Astariz & Iglesias, 2015; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017). As compared to offshore oil and gas platforms, which are typically large, manned structures located in very deep water, marine energy devices are smaller and often located in shallow water where the effects of tides, waves, and currents are more significant (Harris et al., 2006; Paredes et al., 2013; Karimirad et al., 2014; Knappett et al., 2015; Weller et al., 2015a; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Xu et al., 2019; Ford et al., 2020). In the offshore oil and gas sectors, performance and safety considerations require the motion of floating platforms to be minimised whereas, in marine energy, devices may be designed to move or even resonate in specific ways and perhaps within pre-defined excursion limits (Johanning et al., 2006; Paredes et al., 2013; Karimirad et al., 2014; Wave Energy Scotland, 2018). Further, for marine energy, the substructure design represents a much greater proportion of the overall expenditure, the design life is longer, the redundancy requirements can be less stringent (though perhaps not if coupled moorings or shared anchors are employed), and the consequences of mooring line failure (more specifically, the risks of loss of life and environmental pollution) are viewed as less significant (Harris et al., 2006; Johanning et al., 2006; Paredes et al., 2013; Karimirad et al., 2014; Knappett et al., 2015; Weller et al., 2015a; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Xu et al., 2019; Ford et al., 2020).

The large factors of safety and redundancy underlying the existing oil and gas standards indicate that significant cost savings may be achieved, particularly for arrays, by developing more efficient, bespoke design methods and guidelines for marine renewable energy (Paredes et al., 2013; Weller et al., 2015a; Xu et al., 2019). The production, installation, operation, and maintenance of smaller, bespoke components and systems for marine energy also offers the potential to stimulate coastal economies through engagement with smaller shipyards, local navigational experts, etc., which would be beneficial for the social acceptance of these new technologies. Foundations, anchors, and moorings have been identified as key challenge areas for research and innovation in marine energy (Cagney & Gruet, 2019; Villate et al., 2020) and made the focus of many collaborative research and development projects, including GEOWAVE (2012-2015), SAFS (2017-2019), ELASTMOOR (2017-2020), CF2T (2018-2021), UMACK (2018-2021), and TIM (2019-2021). There are also several research and development projects considering the design of novel anchors, mooring systems, and floating platforms for offshore wind turbines, which represent a similar technical and economic challenge: FLOTANT (2019-2022), PIVOTBUOY (2019-2022), COREWIND (2019-2023), etc.

Selkie (2019-2022) is a collaborative marine energy research and development project funded by the European Union's Ireland-Wales Cooperation Programme. Its aim is to develop a set of multi-use tools, templates, standards, and models in key shared technology areas including techno-economic assessment, physical and numerical modelling, data acquisition and analysis, operations and logistics, and foundation and mooring system design. As part of this work, the Selkie consortium will consult

with marine energy technology and project developers, supply chain companies, and partners from complementary research projects to re-examine the existing approaches for foundation and mooring system design and determine the priority areas for potential improvement. For the remainder of the project, the consortium will then work to produce a new, open-source tool to assist with the design of foundations, anchors, and mooring systems for marine energy projects.

The present report constitutes the first deliverable (D5.1) in work package 5 of the Selkie project, which focuses on foundation and mooring system design. Beginning with an overview of the available technology and existing design approaches, the report reviews existing tools for foundation, anchor, and mooring system design with a particular focus on open-source software tools and their applicability to marine energy projects. Its findings will be used to inform the research undertaken in work package 5 and the development of the corresponding Selkie design tool.

The report is laid out as follows: the design considerations and available options regarding station-keeping systems for fixed and floating offshore structures are presented in Section 2; the different design approaches and relevant guidelines are described in Section 3; the most relevant existing open-source design tools are reviewed in Section 4; and the report concludes with Section 5, which summarises the key findings and outlines a framework for the new Selkie foundation and mooring design tool.

2. Station-keeping systems: Design considerations and options

Over the past several decades, the offshore oil and gas industries have developed well-established procedures for the design of station-keeping systems (Carbon Trust, 2005). The adoption of these techniques and practices has been useful for the nascent marine energy industries but it is also clear that bespoke methods and guidelines are needed (Byrne & Houlsby, 2003; Harris et al., 2006; Johanning et al., 2006; Paredes et al., 2013; Villate et al., 2020). As marine energy developers seek to balance the need for bespoke designs with the need for mass production (Byrne & Houlsby, 2003; Johanning et al., 2006), they must consider all available options to reduce their capital and operational expenditure (Weller et al., 2015a).

Given that the financial turnover of a marine energy project is orders of magnitude lower than that of an offshore oil or gas platform (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007), the optimisation of the station-keeping system would have a significant impact on the LCOE (Paredes et al., 2013). This optimisation is complicated, however, by the fact that there is no single, dominant marine energy device and thus no general set of design specifications for a marine energy foundation or mooring system (Harris et al., 2006; Johanning et al., 2006; Wave Energy Scotland, 2018). In wave energy, for instance, there have been more than 1,000 different device prototypes and for many of these, the foundation or mooring system plays a key role in power production (Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Wave Energy Scotland, 2018; Xu et al., 2019).

The following sub-sections describe the key considerations and available options for designing a station-keeping system for a seabed-fixed or floating marine energy device. Little information about best practices has been made publicly available as most devices are still undergoing pre-commercial testing and so, in addition to publications in scientific journals, information has been elicited from industry and academic experts, research reports, and presentations.

To begin, it is important to stress that there is no ‘one-size-fits-all’ model for a foundation or mooring system: each system should be specifically tailored for a given device and location with the objective

being to secure the device against extreme loads and to enable efficient power production and ease of monitoring and maintenance, all whilst avoiding costly over-design and introducing minimal environmental impact (Harris et al., 2006; Natarajan et al., 2016; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Xu et al., 2019). Amongst other considerations, the choice of station-keeping system will depend on the type, scale, mode of operation, and expected design life of the device; as well as the characteristics of the deployment site, including the seabed and soil conditions, water depth, expected environmental loading, allowable excursion limits; and environmental and legislative constraints, including installation, maintenance, and decommissioning requirements (Carbon Trust, 2005; Harris et al., 2006; Johanning et al., 2006; Karimirad et al., 2014; Gómez et al., 2015; Knappett et al., 2015; Weller et al., 2015a; Uihlein & Magagna, 2016; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Xu et al., 2019). At a fundamental level, however, there are only two objective functions to consider: the structural reliability of the system, which is to be maximised, and the total cost, which is to be minimised (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020).

It is also important to note that the deployment of marine energy devices in large arrays will further complicate the design of foundations and mooring systems: dense arrangements will necessitate small seabed footprints and increase the risks of both mooring line entanglement and cascading failures, whilst sparse arrays will increase the likelihood of encountering varied seabed conditions requiring different foundation and anchor types (Johanning et al., 2006; Karimirad et al., 2014; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Xu et al., 2019). Array developers must also leave adequate clearances for vessel access during maintenance intervals and may consider employing modular designs to allow for the removal and replacement of devices and components whilst much of the array remains operational (Harris et al., 2006; Karimirad et al., 2014). The use of shared platforms, moorings, and anchors between different devices could prove a useful means by which to reduce the capital and operational expenditure but are also likely to introduce new and unique design complications (Karimirad et al., 2014; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Abhinav et al., 2020; IRENA, 2020).

2.1. Fixed devices

Marine energy devices are typically secured to the seabed either directly, by means of a rigid foundation, or indirectly, by means of a flexible mooring system comprising an anchor, mooring lines, and perhaps additional components such as clump weights and buoyancy modules. As noted previously, the primary function of the station-keeping system is to secure the devices in place in a reliable and cost-effective manner and to safely absorb and transfer the applied loading without adversely affecting the power performance (Byrne & Houlsby, 2003; Harris et al., 2006; Karimirad et al., 2014; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Xu et al., 2019). To achieve this, it is important to ensure that all system components have adequate strength and durability, and to account for the effects of fatigue, corrosion, and marine growth over the design life (Harris et al., 2006).

Foundations for fixed offshore structures typically resist the applied loading by means of their self-weight, sliding, or overturning resistance, or by making a connection with the seabed which utilises the strength of the surrounding soil or rock. The most common types of foundation for such structures are shown in Figure 1 and described in the following subsections.

2.1.1. Gravity-based foundations

In its simplest form, the gravity-based foundation is lowered to rest on the seabed and the weight of the foundation, along with the friction generated between its base and the underlying seabed, is

Figure 1: Foundation types for fixed marine energy devices (left to right): gravity-based foundation; piled foundation; suction caisson foundation; jacket foundation. Adapted from Aqua-RET (2012).

sufficient to resist the vertical and horizontal loads, as well as overturning moments, applied to the attached device (Thompson et al., 2012). In principle, this is perhaps the simplest means of securing an offshore structure but in practice, seabed levelling and grouting may also be required (Carbon Trust, 2009). These foundations are generally constructed as hollow shells of reinforced concrete, which are transported to site and ballasted with concrete, sand, rock, and/or other materials. The traditional construction allows for rapid manufacturing and customisable design, but the large size and weight of these foundations can create logistical challenges (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020).

Gravity-based foundations are predominantly used in shallow water depths (less than 30m) and well suited to medium or hard soils as well as to complicated geological conditions which might preclude the use of other foundation types (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). Due to the inherent durability of concrete in marine environments, these foundations have low maintenance requirements and, provided that appropriate lifting equipment is available, can be re-positioned and re-used with ease. Gravity-based foundations are less well suited to soft soils and uneven seabeds, however, and, without additional ballast, provide only limited capacity to resist horizontal loading.

Gravity-based foundations have been used to secure many marine energy devices, including the D03 and D10 tidal turbines (Sabella BZH, France) and in the Shetland (Nova Innovation Ltd, UK) and MeyGen (Simec Atlantis Energy Ltd, UK) tidal energy arrays, and have also been selected for the proposed Fécamp (France) and Empire (USA) offshore wind farms.

2.1.2. Pile foundations

Pile foundations are long, open-ended, steel cylinders which can be driven into the seabed using a hammer, vibration, or lowered and grouted into a pre-drilled hole. These foundations utilise the lateral resistance of the surrounding soil as well as the soil-pile friction and end-bearing capacity to resist horizontal loads, vertical loads, and overturning moments (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020).

Piles have a simple geometry defined by their diameter, length, wall thickness, and conical section, and an established supply chain for mass production. Though suited to a wide range of seabed conditions and water depths (Carbon Trust, 2009), piles are predominantly used in sediments and

shallow depths (less than 30m) as the strict rotation tolerances applied to wind turbines make standard piles prohibitively expensive in deeper waters. Pile foundations are often more cost-effective than gravity-based foundations, but the installation of a pile is more expensive and time-consuming, and piles are more difficult to remove at the end of their service life. Piles also require careful assessment of the seabed conditions, and involve hammering or drilling operations which can raise economic and environmental concerns.

Monopiles with diameters greater than 3m are by far the most common foundation type for offshore wind turbines in Europe, having been utilised at the Hornsea (UK) and London Array (UK) developments amongst many others. Pile foundations have also been used to secure some marine energy devices, such as the SeaGen tidal turbine (Marine Current Turbines Ltd, UK) and Oyster wave energy converter (Aquamarine Power Ltd, UK).

2.1.3. Suction caisson foundations

Suction caisson foundations, also called suction piles or suction buckets, are steel cylinders which are closed at the top and generally have much larger diameters (5m or greater) than monopiles (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). They are installed by first allowing the self-weight of the caisson to embed itself in the seabed, after which water is pumped out of the caisson to create a pressure difference which drives it further into the seabed. This suction pressure is not maintained over the lifetime of the structure, however: once installed, these foundations utilise the lateral soil resistance, friction, and their end-bearing capacity (as with piles) in addition to their self-weight to resist the applied loads and moments (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020).

Suction caissons provide an efficient and versatile connection for soft clays and sandy soils but are not suitable for harder seabeds. As with other types of foundations, the large size and weight of the caissons can create logistical challenges and some seabed preparation may be necessary. Similar to gravity-based foundations, suction caissons are (at least in theory) fully removable after their service life. Assuming favourable ground conditions, suction caissons can also be installed more easily and with less underwater noise than pile foundations. However, with these foundations there are also risks of soil liquefaction and concerns regarding the capacity to resist uplift under sustained tensile loading.

Suction caisson foundations are commonly used in the offshore wind energy industry, including at the Hornsea (UK) and Aberdeen Bay (UK) wind farms, but have not yet been used in wave or tidal stream energy projects.

2.1.4. Jacket foundations

Jacket foundations are steel lattice frameworks with three or four legs which are usually secured via grouted connection to piles or suction caissons in the seabed. These foundations have well-established design procedures, having been used for decades in the offshore oil and gas industries (Shi et al., 2013). The light and stiff lattice structure enables a push-pull action to resist horizontal and vertical loads as well as overturning moments.

Whereas piles are typically the most efficient solution in shallower water depths (less than 30m), jacket structures are often the most efficient for deeper waters (usually 30-70m). The variety of lattice structures and seabed connection types also make jacket foundations highly adaptable to different seabed conditions. Due to their hydrodynamically 'transparent' design, these foundations are also less

exposed to wave and current loading than other foundation types. However, their reliance on pile or suction caisson foundations makes their installation more expensive and time-consuming, and subject to the same environmental concerns regarding underwater noise. In addition, jacket foundations often have a large seabed footprint and incorporate grouted connections and a great many welded joints which require careful inspection.

Other than monopiles, jacket structures are the most common foundation type for offshore wind turbines in Europe, having been utilised at the Moray East (UK) and East Anglia One (UK) wind farms amongst many others. As of yet, however, jacket foundations do not appear to have been used in wave or tidal stream projects.

2.2. Floating devices

Mooring systems for offshore structures must be designed to meet many different requirements: to secure the floater within the allowable excursion limits; to absorb and transfer loads to the anchor(s) but not the electrical power cable(s); to ensure that mooring lines do not become entangled or collide with the seabed; to accommodate changes in water level due to tides; and to be cost-effective, easily maintainable, and introduce only minimal environmental impact (e.g., Harris et al., 2006; Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Karimirad et al., 2014; Wave Energy Scotland, 2018; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). In the case of marine energy devices, mooring systems must also be carefully designed to enable efficient energy conversion: sufficiently flexible to minimise the loading on the floater, mooring lines, and anchors, yet sufficiently stiff to provide any reaction forces necessary for power generation (Harris et al., 2006; Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Paredes et al., 2013).

The development of general guidelines to enable reliable yet cost-effective mooring systems is a challenging task because, just as there is diversity amongst marine energy device types, there is diversity amongst mooring system types and requirements (Harris et al., 2006; Johanning et al., 2006). Systems can be static or dynamic, depending on the stiffness or flexibility requirements (Harris et al., 2006); symmetrical or asymmetrical (Xu et al., 2019); and include one or many anchors and mooring lines (Xu et al., 2019; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). Moorings can also be passive, providing only station-keeping capabilities; active, exerting a significant influence on the dynamic response of the device; or reactive, forming an integral part of the power take-off system (Karimirad et al., 2014; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017). In addition to the characteristics of the device and deployment site, the design of the mooring system will depend on reliability, safety, and economic considerations (Harris et al., 2006; Karimirad et al., 2014). Given the limited experience of marine energy deployments, a degree of redundancy would also be desirable (Harris et al., 2006; Villate et al., 2020): although a non-redundant system would cost less initially, it is expected that a system with redundancy would have a lower associated risk, less downtime, and thus lower costs overall (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020).

Until recently, moorings have been of secondary concern to marine energy designers (Harris et al., 2006) but given their influence over the dynamics of floating devices, it is vital to consider the contributions of the mooring system early in the design process (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007). The following subsections describe the most common types of mooring system, mooring line material, and anchors for floating offshore structures.

Figure 2: Mooring system types for floating marine energy devices (left to right): catenary mooring; taut mooring; wave- (or S-) type mooring. Adapted from Aqua-RET (2012).

2.2.1. Mooring system types

Floating marine energy devices are typically secured by catenary mooring, taut mooring, or some variation or combination of these two system types (Weller et al., 2015a). Wave- (or S-) type mooring configurations can be created by incorporating buoyancy modules to provide additional flexibility and clump weights to provide additional stiffness and/or reduce the length of mooring lines (Harris et al., 2006; Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Johanning et al., 2007). These configurations can reduce the effects of the mooring line on the dynamics of the floater and reduce the effects of peak ('snap' or 'snatch') loading, which is a key design driver (Harris et al., 2006). Additional components to reduce peak mooring line loads by active and passive means are also available (e.g., Wave Energy Scotland, 2018). The most common types of mooring system are shown in Figure 2 and described as follows.

In a catenary mooring system, the floater is connected to the anchor by one or more heavy steel chains, and the restoring forces are generated primarily by the weight of these chains which adopt, under equilibrium conditions, the shape of a catenary curve (Harris et al., 2006; Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007). These systems have well-established design criteria, and can allow the floater considerable freedom of movement (Harris et al., 2006; Karimirad et al., 2014; Xu et al., 2019; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). The main advantage of a catenary mooring system is that because the anchor is subject to predominantly horizontal loads, the system is compatible with a broad range of anchor types (Karimirad et al., 2014; GeoWave, 2015; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). The main disadvantage is that to ensure that the imposed vertical loads are reacted solely by their weight, long mooring lines are required: usually 3-5 times the water depth (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Xu et al., 2019). The greater length and weight of the mooring lines naturally results in a larger seabed footprint (and hence larger potential exclusion zone for marine species and other users of the marine space), higher installation costs, and increased risks of mooring line entanglement (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Karimirad et al., 2014; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020).

Catenary mooring systems have been used to secure many marine energy devices, including the Pelamis P1 and P2 wave energy converters (Pelamis Wave Power Ltd, Portugal; UK) and the ATIR floating tidal energy platform (Magallanes Renovables SL, UK), and will also be used to secure the new Orbital O2 tidal turbine (Orbital Marine Power Ltd, UK).

In a taut mooring system, the floater is connected to the anchor by one or more pre-tensioned steel wires or synthetic ropes, and the restoring forces are generated primarily by the stiffness and elasticity of the mooring lines (Harris et al., 2006; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). These systems also have well-established design criteria and although less well-suited to large tidal ranges than catenary moorings,

can secure the floater within a smaller excursion envelope and with a greater amount of stability (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). The main advantage of a taut mooring system is that they require much shorter lines than a catenary system, and so can ensure a smaller seabed footprint and hence exclusion zone, particularly in deeper waters (Karimirad et al., 2014; GeoWave, 2015; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). As noted previously, a stiff taut mooring system may also be required to provide the necessary reaction forces for power generation. The main disadvantages are that installation procedures are more complicated: lines must be carefully sized and pre-tensioned to ensure that they have sufficient elasticity to absorb the imposed loads without overloading. In addition, taut moorings require more expensive anchors which can resist vertical as well as horizontal loads (Karimirad et al., 2014; GeoWave, 2015; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020).

Taut mooring systems have also been used to secure many marine energy devices, including the Tocardo (Tocardo BV, UK) and PLAT-O (Sustainable Marine Energy Ltd, UK) floating tidal energy platforms and the CorPower C3 wave energy converter (CorPower Ocean, UK).

The offshore industry has developed several other mooring system types which might prove useful in marine energy applications (e.g., Wave Energy Scotland, 2018). Semi-taut systems seek to combine the advantages of taut and catenary moorings by incorporating shorter taut lines to extend the application of catenary systems into deeper waters (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). Catenary (CALM) and single anchor leg mooring (SALM) systems are widely used to allow floaters to ‘weathervane’ around buoys which have been moored using multiple catenary or single taut lines, respectively, but the large excursion envelopes might make these systems unsuitable for arrays (Harris et al., 2006; Xu et al., 2019). Other established station-keeping systems, including articulated leg moorings, articulated loading columns, fixed tower and turret moorings, active moorings, and dynamic positioning systems, are generally viewed as less suitable to marine energy projects but may prove useful under certain circumstances (Harris et al., 2006).

2.2.2. Mooring line materials

The most common mooring line materials for offshore renewable energy devices are steel chain, steel wire, and synthetic rope, or some combination of these different material types (Johanning et al., 2006). Although cost is always an important factor in the design of such systems, the choice of mooring line material is more likely to be based on physical properties such as break strength, axial and bending stiffness, and impact on floater motion, as well as reliability and design life (Harris et al., 2006; Johanning et al., 2006; Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Wave Energy Scotland, 2018; Xu et al., 2019; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020).

Steel chains have been used for decades in mooring applications, most often in catenary mooring systems. Different sizes and grades of chain are available for different applications, and the maintenance intervals are predictable (Harris et al., 2006; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). Additional lengths of (‘ground’) chain may be laid along the seabed because their weight can be used to minimise the vertical loading transferred to the anchors (Harris et al., 2006; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). Due to their favourable bending properties, chains are also used in the water column and near the sea surface but become less cost-efficient in deeper waters as the weight increases with the required length (Harris et al., 2006; GeoWave, 2015; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). However, chains are also subject to corrosion and significant issues can arise regarding fatigue loading, twist, and out-of-plane bending.

Steel wire is lighter and more flexible than steel chain, and many different types are available: spiral strand, multi-strand, six-strand, etc. (Harris et al., 2006; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). Due to their high

breaking-load capacities, steel wires are also suitable for semi-taut and taut mooring systems. These wires are typically more expensive than chains, however, and more susceptible to damage by corrosion and fretting (Harris et al., 2006; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020).

Synthetic ropes are lighter and more flexible than both steel chains and steel wires and, depending on the material chosen, can be both more durable and more cost-effective (Weller et al., 2015a; GeoWave, 2015; Xu et al., 2019; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). Many different types of synthetic rope are available (polyester, aramid, nylon, etc.) and their high breaking strength means that they can be used in both taut and catenary mooring systems (Harris et al., 2006; Weller et al., 2015a). Synthetic ropes are also corrosion-immune and have elastic properties which could be used to reduce peak mooring line loads (Karimirad et al., 2014; Weller et al., 2015a; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). Further, these ropes can be manufactured to be (neutrally) buoyant, which could greatly simplify offshore operations (Harris et al., 2006). Given that long-term experience is not available, however, synthetic ropes require high safety factors which increase system costs (Harris et al., 2006). Further research is also required to better understand the non-linear and time-dependent load extension properties of these ropes as creep or heat generation could cause sudden failure or degrade their performance over time (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Karimirad et al., 2014; Xu et al., 2019; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020).

2.2.3. Anchor types

The primary requirements of a mooring line anchor are to resist large and often complex loading (horizontal, vertical, or both) and to be both easily deployable and cost-effective (GeoWave, 2015; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). The type and design of anchor can either determine, or be determined by, the type of mooring system, but also depends on the characteristics of the deployment site (the magnitude and direction of environmental loading as well as the required holding capacity) as well as on the cost and operational practicalities (Harris et al., 2006; Karimirad et al., 2014; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). Demonstration projects for floating marine energy devices typically use either gravity-based or drag-embedment anchors, which are often selected for their simplicity rather than their geotechnical or economic efficiency (Knappett et al., 2015). For arrays comprising large numbers of devices, however, more efficient types of anchors will be required to reduce material and installation costs and perhaps enable the sharing of anchors between multiple devices (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Knappett et al., 2015; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017). The most common anchor types are shown in Figure 3 and described as follows.

Several of the available anchor types utilise the same principles as those used to design foundations for fixed devices, and holding capacities can be estimated from manufacturers' catalogues, standard design tables, or semi-empirical models. Gravity-based anchors, also known as deadweight or clump-weight anchors, are one of the most common types used in marine energy projects, having been used to secure the ATIR and Tocado floating tidal energy platforms, the CorPower C3 wave energy converter, and many other marine energy devices. These anchors are simple to manufacture and applicable to a broad range of seabed conditions, but also expensive and geotechnically inefficient (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). Pin-piled anchors, such as those used to secure the Ursa tension leg oil platform (USA), can be more cost-efficient than gravity-based anchors and ensure a smaller seabed footprint, but require specialised installation equipment and high-quality geotechnical data to minimise the risk of pile refusal (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Karimirad et al., 2014). Suction anchors, such as those used in the Hywind Scotland offshore wind farm (Equinor and Masdar, UK) can provide efficient station-keeping solutions which generate less noise during the

Figure 3: Anchor types for floating marine energy devices (left to right): drag-embedment anchor; drag-in plate anchor; screw anchor; dynamically installed anchor. Adapted from Aqua-RET (2012).

installation phase than pin-pile anchors, but also require favourable seabed conditions and sophisticated deployment procedures (Harris et al., 2006; Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Knappett et al., 2015).

Drag-embedment anchors, also known as drag or fluke anchors, are another common anchor type for marine energy devices and will be used to secure the 500kW OE35 wave energy converter (Ocean Energy Ltd, USA) in its upcoming pilot tests. On being dragged across the seabed, these anchors are designed to penetrate and embed themselves, either partially or fully, and to resist primarily horizontal loading in one principal direction (Harris et al., 2006; Karimirad et al., 2014; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). The holding capacity of this type of anchor is generated by the passive resistance of the wedge of soil in front of the anchor and so depends on the weight, area, and embedment depth as well as the type, slope, and other characteristics of the soil (Karimirad et al., 2014; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020).

Drag-embedment anchors have been widely used in offshore applications and shown to be both simple to install and well-suited to resisting large horizontal loads (Harris et al., 2006; Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Karimirad et al., 2014; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). These anchors are also less expensive and more efficient than gravity-based anchors, and their design requires much less geotechnical data than would be needed for pile anchors (Knappett et al., 2015). However, drag-embedment anchors are also less well-suited to hard soil conditions and resisting vertical loads than gravity-based anchors (Harris et al., 2006; Karimirad et al., 2014; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020), require a large seabed footprint, and can be subject to slow drift, which can necessitate recovery and re-deployment (Harnois et al., 2012; Karimirad et al., 2014).

The requirement to resist significant vertical loading naturally requires a more advanced anchor design (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007). This more involved and hence expensive design process can be offset, however, by the fact that vertically loaded anchors can be much lighter and placed more accurately than either gravity-based or drag-embedment anchors, resist significant loading in any direction, and enable shorter mooring lines and smaller seabed footprints (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Karimirad et al., 2014; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020).

The drag-in plate anchor, for instance, operates much like a drag-embedment anchor but incorporates an adjustable angle between the horizontal fluke and vertical shank which allows the anchor to penetrate much deeper into the seabed (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). This greater embedment depth

enables the drag-in plate anchor to provide greater uplift resistance than the drag-embedment anchor and often do so with a more efficient design (Knappett et al., 2015). This anchor requires quite favourable seabed conditions to generate the holding capacity, however; drag-in plate anchors require deep layers of clay and are not well-suited to either very soft soils, which provide insufficient holding capacity, or very hard soils, which provide resistance to embedment (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). The installation of a drag-in plate anchor also typically requires a vessel with considerable bollard-pull capabilities (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007) but embedded plate anchors can also be installed by other means, including suction.

Drilled rock anchors (or 'micro-piles'), such as those used to secure the PLAT-O tidal energy platform, can also be used to secure devices against significant uplift loading. Screw-type anchors, comprising long steel shafts with one or more helices, could provide similar uplift capacities to plate anchors (Cerfontaine et al., 2019). Assuming that practical methods can be designed and validated, the installation of screw anchors may also require lower bollard-pull capacities than drag-in plate anchors and generate less noise than pin-piled anchors (Cerfontaine et al., 2019).

Dynamically installed anchors, which are also known as deep-penetrating, drop, or torpedo anchors, offer an alternative station-keeping option. These anchors comprise heavy steel cylinders with conical tips which are released from vessels to fall freely through the water column and embed themselves in the seabed below (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). The primary advantage of these systems is that they can be easily installed in very deep water and require much less geophysical and geotechnical information about the underlying seabed. Dynamically installed anchors can be deployed with minimal handling requirements (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020) and, once installed, can provide significant resistance to both horizontal and vertical loads. The primary disadvantage is that it is difficult to predict the final embedment depth, orientation, and thus holding capacity. The applicability of these anchors is also limited to deep, soft, cohesive, and homogeneous soils (Knappett et al., 2015) and their re-positioning and retrieval represent considerable challenges. Nevertheless, torpedo anchors have been used to secure the Petrobras FPSOP-50 offshore oil and gas platform (Brazil) and their potential use in marine energy applications has been explored as part of the GeoWave project (see GeoWave, 2015).

3. Station-keeping systems: Design approaches and guidelines

The design methods and standards used by the offshore oil and gas industries have been developed with marine safety and environmental protection in mind and incorporate a wealth of knowledge and experience which can be readily applied to marine energy projects (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007). Marine energy developments are quite different from offshore oil and gas developments, however, in that the assets are more broadly distributed across a given seabed area, which means that greater numbers of smaller station-keeping systems are required, each of which must be nonetheless reliable, cost-effective, and designed to introduce only minimal environmental impact.

The design process is iterative and makes use of both generic modelling techniques and site-specific information to assess the reliability and performance of the foundation, anchor, or mooring system (Johanning et al., 2006; Heath et al., 2014; Müller et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2019). Water level, wind, wave, current, seabed, and soil data are used along with device characteristics and engineering judgement to identify a preliminary system type to be analysed (Carbon Trust, 2005; Johanning et al., 2006; Heath et al., 2014; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Xu et al., 2019). The type of analysis required to design an offshore structure is determined by the form and function of the device as well as the local environmental conditions and expected loading (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Natarajan et al., 2016;

Müller et al., 2018). It is also important to establish design philosophies regarding transport, installation, maintenance, redundancy, fatigue, etc. (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020).

The general design approach involves examining various failure modes and corresponding limit states, meaning conditions beyond which the structure or component no longer satisfies the design requirements (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). Failure modes for foundations, anchors, and mooring systems include yielding, buckling, fracture, deformation, subsidence, uplift, pull-out, overturning, and sliding (Heath et al., 2014), whilst limit states typically consider the ultimate resistance (the ultimate limit state, or ULS) and serviceability (the serviceability limit state, or SLS) of the structure under normal and extreme operating conditions, as well as its performance under fatigue loading (the fatigue limit state, or FLS) and operational failure (the accidental limit state, or ALS) (DTOcean, 2015; Natarajan et al., 2016; Müller et al., 2018). Safety factors are also applied, with values (from a minimum of 1 to values of 2 or greater) assigned in accordance with the expected consequences of failure, to provide adequate margins of safety (Paredes et al., 2013; DTOcean, 2015). Depending on the design standards selected, the design loads can have different return periods, can be considered separately or in combination, and different safety margins can be recommended for either the entire structure or individual components (Paredes et al., 2013; Weller et al., 2014; DTOcean, 2015).

The preliminary design is then tested against different design load cases (normal operation, operation with fault, emergency shutdown, etc.) to ensure that the structure is fit for purpose but not over-engineered (Weller et al., 2014; Natarajan et al., 2016; Müller et al., 2018). For a normal failure consequence class, which implies a moderate risk of human injury and moderate environmental and economic consequences, designers typically aim for less than one major single accident every 10,000 installation years (Weller et al., 2014; DTOcean, 2015). Given the complexity of the interactions between the device, environment, and seabed, however, it is also essential to undertake numerical modelling to predict the performance of the system and ensure an efficient design (Byrne & Houlsby, 2003; Heath et al., 2014; Weller et al., 2014; Natarajan et al., 2016; Müller et al., 2018). The choice of numerical model will again depend on the specifics of the design problem and, given the range of environmental and operating conditions to be considered, require engineering judgement to balance the desired accuracy of results against the computational cost (Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Natarajan et al., 2016; Müller et al., 2018).

Design methods and standards are guided and updated by practical experience, which ensures the continuous improvement of the established practices. The following subsections describe the design methods and standards most relevant to station-keeping systems for fixed and floating offshore structures.

3.1. Design goals and drivers

For fixed devices, a detailed understanding of how the foundation system transfers load from the structure to the surrounding soil is essential (Byrne & Houlsby, 2003). For floating devices, the stiffness of the mooring system, which is a function of the mooring configuration, line materials, and line pretensions, must be characterised to understand how the system will respond to different floater motions, and to calculate the corresponding line tensions and potential for fatigue damage (Johanning et al., 2006; Pillai et al., 2019). The excursions of the floating body are a function of both the magnitude of the external forces and the mooring stiffness (Johanning et al., 2006), so it is vital to understand the influence of the mooring system on power production (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007). Structures must also be configured such that the natural frequencies either minimise, in the case of devices for which performance does not depend on motion, or maximise, for motion-dependent devices, the likelihood

of resonance with the external forcing frequencies (Johanning et al., 2006; Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Xu et al., 2019).

For submerged devices such as seabed-mounted tidal turbines, the key design drivers are the high current loads and subsequent effects on foundations and cables (Villate et al., 2020). For surface-piercing devices such as fixed wind turbines, cyclic and non-coincident wind and wave loads are the most important design considerations (Byrne & Houlsby, 2003). For floating wind turbines and marine energy devices, meanwhile, designs may be driven by the operational wind speeds and sea states, where the thrust force dominates the mean offset, or by the extreme wave conditions and associated peak loading on anchors and mooring lines (Harris et al., 2006; Villate et al., 2020).

3.2. Design approaches and models

Models which have been developed either within other ocean engineering fields or specifically for marine renewable energy can be used to analyse and optimise the performance of single devices or arrays, calculate extreme and fatigue loads, and evaluate different foundation and mooring system designs (Davidson & Ringwood, 2017). One notable challenge in selecting or creating such a model is the broad frequency range of environmental inputs and substructure responses: environmental loads are typically separated into constant, low-frequency, and high- (or wave-) frequency components (Johanning et al., 2006; Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007) which, for simplicity, are often considered separately (Davidson & Ringwood, 2017). Another challenge is that the data and experience required to validate such models is difficult and expensive to obtain, particularly from energetic marine environments. A variety of different modelling techniques are available but simpler and more computationally efficient models are typically favoured for the initial design phases, with more accurate and computationally expensive models only introduced as the analysis becomes more refined (Müller et al., 2016; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017).

3.2.1. Static and quasi-static analyses

In the initial phase of the design process, static analytical techniques are used to identify a preliminary type and configuration, as well as materials and dimensions, for the foundation and mooring system (Johanning et al., 2006; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017). Static analyses assume constant loads (weight, buoyancy, steady current and wind loads, and mean wave drift forces) and static restoring forces, and can be used to calculate the holding capacity and stability of an anchor or foundation, or the line tension and equilibrium position for a floater secured by a particular mooring configuration (Paredes et al., 2013; Weller et al., 2014; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Xu et al., 2019). These analyses are simple, computationally efficient, and can be used to ensure that a given station-keeping system provides sufficient resistance to the simplified load conditions and does so with an appropriate seabed footprint and whilst keeping the natural frequencies and floater excursions within the specified limits (Johanning et al., 2006; Müller et al., 2016).

Quasi-static analyses, which assume that the structure and component motion is uniform and linear between two given positions, can also be used to investigate how a station-keeping system will respond to different load combinations and ensure compliance with design standards for different limit states (Johanning et al., 2006; Weller et al., 2014; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017). Static and quasi-static techniques neglect the dynamic nature of the system motions and restoring forces, as well as hydrodynamic and inertial loading, but can provide a useful starting point for more advanced analyses (Müller et al., 2016; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017).

3.2.2. Dynamic and coupled dynamic analyses

Dynamic analyses use more advanced numerical techniques to account for the fact that the environmental loading and system responses are dynamic in nature. By incorporating inertia, stiffness, damping, and fluid excitation force terms, these analyses, which typically utilise finite element techniques to solve equations of motion in the time or frequency domain (Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Pillai et al., 2019), can be used to investigate elasticity, stress and strain, cyclic loading and fatigue, as well as the interactions between the station-keeping and power take-off systems (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007; Paredes et al., 2013; Weller et al., 2014; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017). Though extreme loads have, historically, been calculated using quasi-static analyses with safety factors of 2 or 3, dynamic analyses are particularly useful for estimating the peak mooring line tensions and anchor holding capacities (Weller et al., 2014; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017).

To accurately assess the system response, dynamic simulations must be performed for each operating condition and sea state (Pillai et al., 2019). This is typically accomplished by first running many simulations in the frequency domain, where calculations are less computationally expensive, and then running a few critical cases in the time domain, which is more effective in capturing dynamic motion and loading (Davidson & Ringwood, 2017; Pillai et al., 2019). Coupled dynamic analyses, which solve different sets of equations of motion simultaneously, can be used to account for interactions such as those between the marine environment, floater, moorings, and power take-off system (Johanning et al., 2006; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017). These analyses are more computationally intensive than uncoupled analysis methods but, depending on the fidelity of the different input models and the design problem in question, can provide much valuable insight (Müller et al., 2016; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017).

Owing to their placement in the most energetic ocean environments, marine energy devices will experience much greater dynamic motion than existing offshore structures, which means that the quasi-static, decoupled, and linearised frequency-domain analyses typically used in offshore design may be less accurate when assessing device performance (Ikhennicheu et al., 2020). Mooring analyses traditionally make use of linear wave theory, but in energetic sea states it will be important to include the effects of viscosity, wave breaking, overtopping, and perhaps wave-current interactions (Cheng & Lin, 2018). Floating devices may experience wave slam loading which might require more sophisticated analysis methods (computational fluid dynamics, smooth particle hydrodynamics, etc.), and novel systems will also require validation with small-scale physical tests (Carbon Trust, 2005; Paredes et al., 2013).

3.2.3. Commercial design software

The final design will typically utilise either an extended quasi-static design procedure or a fully coupled dynamic analysis (Paredes et al., 2013). There are many commercial software packages available to perform such analyses, including ANSYS Aqwa, MOSES, WAMIT, etc., for floater dynamics; Ariane, DeepLines, OrcaFlex, etc., for mooring dynamics; and Abaqus FEA, PLAXIS, Sesam, etc., for anchors, foundations, and soil-structure interactions (Weller et al., 2014). Naturally, however, these packages have different requirements and capabilities, and it is not yet clear how the different codes compare or how well-suited a given code is to marine energy design (Heath et al., 2014; Weller et al., 2014). Further, although existing commercial tools may have certain coupling capabilities, it is likely that these packages will need to be linked to custom-made or in-house numerical methods to account for novel designs, bespoke power take-off systems, etc. (Heath et al., 2014; Weller et al., 2014; Davidson & Ringwood, 2017). The commercial software packages which are most relevant to the design of

station-keeping systems for marine energy devices are described briefly as follows; the most relevant open-source tools are discussed in greater detail in Section 4.

Commercial hydrodynamic analysis tools include ANSYS Aqwa (ANSYS Inc.), MOSES (Bentley Systems), and WAMIT (WAMIT, Inc.). These software packages utilise different numerical methods, but can each be used to examine the interactions between ocean waves and floating bodies, and calculate the hydrodynamic coefficients required for motion and response analyses. Commercial mooring dynamics software tools include Ariane (Bureau Veritas), Deeplines (Principia), OrcaFlex (Orcina), and SIMA (SINTEF). These packages use static and dynamic analysis methods to calculate the six-degree-of-freedom motions of floating bodies and the resulting profiles, offsets, and tensions of multi-component mooring lines. Commercial finite element analysis tools include Abaqus FEA (Simulia), PLAXIS (Bentley Systems), and Sesam (DNV GL). These packages can also be used to perform static and dynamic analyses of fluids, structures, and materials, and their soil-structure analysis capabilities make them well-suited to the design of anchors and offshore foundations. Moreover, a number of the aforementioned commercial software packages have developed specific tools for the design and analysis of offshore fixed and floating wind turbines.

3.3. Design standards and guidelines

Marine energy designs have been based primarily on methods and standards developed by the oil and gas industries, which have been working in offshore and deep-water environments for more than 70 years (Fitzgerald & Bergdahl, 2007). Designs and operations for offshore oil and gas developments are informed, in turn, by guidance from certification agencies such as DNV GL and the American Petroleum Institute (API), which have provided a wealth of understanding and practical experience leading to improved fabrication processes and fewer operational failures (DTOcean, 2015; Weller et al., 2015a). Whereas in the offshore oil and gas industries, the economic costs of development are viewed as a lower priority than time scale, reliability, and safety considerations, cost is a primary driver in marine energy (Weller et al., 2014). Economies of scale in marine energy will most likely be achieved through long-term deployments providing reliable failure rate statistics and design convergence enabling the mass production of components (DTOcean, 2015). Cost savings in the design phase may also have a multiplicative effect, resulting in lower operations and maintenance costs (DTOcean, 2015).

Insights from the shipping, aquaculture, and offshore wind energy industries may also be relevant to marine energy (Harris et al., 2006; DTOcean, 2015). Though fish farms are often located in sheltered waters, like marine energy devices they are designed for autonomous operation, with personnel boarding only for occasional maintenance, and the consequences of station-keeping system failure are relatively low (Paredes et al., 2013; Weller et al., 2015a). Guidelines for the design of fixed and floating offshore wind turbines appear particularly relevant to marine energy devices (see Gujer & Kretschmer, 2015), but standards for floating wind turbines are still in the early stages of development and additional guidance will be required to account for the motion-dependency of many marine energy devices as well as the greater emphasis on inter-array hydrodynamic interactions (Paredes et al., 2013; Weller et al., 2015a).

In addition to DNV GL, the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), and the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO), organisations such as the Carbon Trust and European Marine Energy Centre (EMEC) have been working to develop bespoke guidelines for marine energy projects. Although these guidelines have recommended lower failure consequence classes for marine energy, the load coefficients are still largely based on oil and gas standards (Paredes et al., 2013; Karimirad et al., 2014; Weller et al., 2014). With limited operational experience, it is difficult to determine the

appropriate safety factors for novel technologies and new approaches may be required to ensure that existing standards are not so onerous as to hinder their development (Sandström et al., 2016). The standards and guidelines which are most relevant to the design of station-keeping systems for marine energy devices are described as follows.

The API is one of the largest trade associations for the oil and gas industries, which also provides guidance and recommendations for the analysis, design, fabrication, transportation, installation, and inspection of temporary and permanent offshore structures. The API has produced many standards which are relevant to the design of marine energy devices, including those on fixed steel structures such as caissons and jackets (API, 2014a; 2019), floating platforms (API, 2011) and station-keeping systems (API, 2005), synthetic mooring ropes (API, 2014b), and in-service inspections (API, 2008).

DNV GL is an international classification society with interests in, amongst other sectors, shipping, oil and gas, and renewable energy. Although not generally accepted as international standards (Sandström et al., 2016), DNV GL provides principles, technical requirements, and guidance relevant to marine energy, free of charge, in the form of design recommendations for fixed structures including foundations and connections (DNV GL, 2017; 2019), floating structures including mooring lines and anchors (DNV GL, 2020a), as well as mooring line materials such as chains (DNV GL, 2018a), steel wires (DNV GL, 2020b), and fibre ropes (DNV GL, 2018b), etc. DNV GL have also produced specific design recommendations for fixed and floating offshore wind turbines (DNV GL, 2018c; 2018d) and wave and tidal stream energy devices (DNV GL, 2008; 2015a; 2015b).

EMEC is a world-leading test and research centre for wave and tidal stream energy devices. In addition to providing expertise and assistance to prototype developers, EMEC has also produced, free of charge, guidance and recommendations for the design of wave and tidal energy converters and the assessment of device performance and reliability (see Davies, 2009). The EMEC guidelines have been designed to complement the relevant ISO standards and rank the quality of evidence used in assessing device performance, from expert opinions to validated numerical simulations and sea trials (Sandström et al., 2016). The guidelines illustrate design procedures which have since been adopted by the IEC and other organisations and EMEC has also prepared, in association with RenewableUK, guidance on health and safety procedures for the marine energy industries (RenewableUK, 2008).

The IEC is an international standards organisation which prepares and publishes international standards on electrical, electronic, and related technology. It has published well-received and widely adopted technical specifications and guidelines for the offshore energy industry. Amongst the most relevant are the TC 88 documents, which cover all aspects of design for fixed and floating offshore wind turbines from site suitability studies (IEC, 2020) to safety considerations (IEC, 2019) and design life extension (IEC, 2018a). The IEC has also provided design requirements for marine energy systems: its TC 114 documents include guidance on assessing the performance of wave and tidal energy devices (IEC, 2012; 2013), mooring system design (IEC, 2015), prototype testing (IEC, 2018b), etc.

The ISO is an international, non-governmental organisation which promotes worldwide proprietary, industrial, and commercial standards. It has enabled groups of international experts to form technical committees and produce guidance documents on many different topics, and often collaborates with the IEC in setting standards for electrical and electronic technology. The ISO has produced a great many standards for the offshore oil and gas, shipping, and marine technology industries, including specific requirements for fixed steel and concrete structures (ISO, 2020a; 2020b), floating structures and station-keeping systems (ISO, 2019; 2020c), geotechnical and foundation design considerations (ISO, 2017), and port and marine operations (ISO, 2020d). ISO standards are often referenced by other guidance documents published by DNV GL, the IEC, etc.

Other organisations, such as the American Bureau of Shipping (ABS) and European Committee for Standardisation (CEN), have also developed standards and guidelines which may be relevant to marine energy applications: on geotechnical and structural design techniques (CEN, 2010; 2014), offshore installation methods (ABS, 2018), and approaches for the review and approval of novel offshore concepts (ABS, 2017).

4. Station-keeping systems: Open-source design tools

In the previous section, it was shown that foundations, anchors, and mooring systems are designed using an iterative engineering approach: static, quasi-static, dynamic, or coupled analysis techniques are used to investigate specific failure modes and limit states for a given system type and deployment location. Analytical or simplified numerical methods can be used in the initial stages of the design process whilst more advanced analyses are typically undertaken using an industry-standard commercial software package (Johanning et al., 2006), custom-made numerical methods, and perhaps novel optimisation techniques (e.g., Pillai et al., 2019). In addition to commercial design software, there are open-source tools which can be used to assist with the design and analysis of foundations, anchors, and mooring systems. Naturally, these open-source tools cannot provide as much detail to the designer as the commercial software, but they do offer the opportunity to quickly and inexpensively generate a design which is sufficient for a feasibility study and further analysis using more sophisticated methods (Weller et al., 2015b).

In recent years, funders of national and international research projects have encouraged the development of FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) data and the open sharing of tools and methods. Accordingly, there now exists a range of open-source software packages, documented in online catalogues such as OpenORE (<https://openore.org/>), MRE CodeHub (<https://mrecodehub.org/>), and PRIMRE (https://openei.org/wiki/PRIMRE/Code_Catalog), to assist with various aspects of the design of marine energy systems, including OpenFOAM (the OpenFOAM Foundation Ltd) for computational fluid dynamics, NEMOH (École Centrale de Nantes) for multi-body dynamics, and SAM (the US National Renewable Energy Laboratory, or NREL) for power performance and financial analysis.

The following subsections review the open-source tools most relevant to the design of foundations, anchors, and mooring systems for marine energy devices. Particular focus is placed on the integrated set of decision-support tools provided by the DTOcean and DTOceanPlus projects, given how similar the aims of these projects are to that of Selkie. The findings of this review will be used to inform the development of the corresponding Selkie design tool, ideas for which are discussed in Section 5.

4.1. DTOcean

The DTOcean project (Optimal design tools for ocean energy arrays, 2013-2016) was funded by the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme and produced a suite of open-source decision-support tools to assist in the development of the first generation of marine energy arrays. The project provides a software package with a graphical user interface which enables designers to generate a spatial grid and model marine energy devices in arrays. This interface is linked to design modules in five key areas (array hydrodynamics, electrical sub-systems, moorings and foundations, installation, and operations and maintenance) which are then combined into a global decision tool which assesses the prospective development in terms of power performance, economics, reliability, lifecycle logistics,

Figure 4: Data flow in the DTOcean station-keeping system module: inputs; calculation submodules, including foundation and mooring design; and outputs. Adapted from Weller et al. (2015b).

and environmental impact (Heath et al., 2014; Nava et al., 2019a). The original (version 1) and revised (version 2) DTOcean codes and user manuals are available at: <http://dtoceanplus.eu/tools>.

As shown in Figure 4, the DTOcean station-keeping system module comprises five sub-modules relating to the system and environmental loads, mooring system, anchors and foundations, electrical power cable, and foundation for the electrical substation (Weller et al., 2015b). Inputs in the form of design parameters and constraints are obtained either from the user, other design modules, or a database of default soil, material, and cost data (Weller et al., 2015b). The primary outputs are the proposed configuration and bill of materials for the station-keeping system, which are used to inform subsequent modules and assess the proposed array design in terms of cost, reliability, and environmental impact (DTOcean, 2015; Weller et al., 2015b). The different design modules are first run sequentially, with the foundation and mooring system module initially provided only information about the arrangements of the devices and electrical infrastructure, and then iteratively, as feedback from the logistics, control, and operations modules are used to refine the design in each area (Weller et al., 2015b).

Whilst acknowledging the need for more sophisticated numerical techniques to account for complex loading and soil-structure interactions, the DTOcean consortium elected to use simplified design approaches, incorporating safety factors to account for performance and reliability uncertainties, to ensure that the simulations could be run within a reasonable time frame (Heath et al., 2014; Weller et al., 2014; 2015b). The station-keeping design module adopts the iterative limit state design approach outlined in the Handbook for Marine Geotechnical Engineering (Thompson et al., 2012), in which reasonable or convenient system dimensions (the number and mass of mooring lines, size and weight of foundations, penetration depth of anchors, etc.) are first estimated based on the local seabed and soil conditions; the system is then analysed to determine the resistance to external forces and ensure compliance with the desired functions; and the analysis is repeated with revised system dimensions if the design is found to be inadequate, over-designed, impractical, or unduly expensive (Heath et al., 2014; Weller et al., 2014; 2015b).

The station-keeping module is informed by look-up tables which compare the performance and associated costs, per soil type, for different anchors and foundations and enables customisation by allowing users to select between different relevant standards and modify safety factors (Heath et al.,

2014; Weller et al., 2015b). Design procedures are also simplified by considering only static and quasi-static analysis methods (neglecting dynamic or cyclic load effects); restricting the number of relevant load cases, operational conditions, and limit states; neglecting, for the most part, the structural analysis of anchors and foundations; and not considering the effects of station-keeping systems on power performance (Weller et al., 2015b).

For fixed devices, a decision tree with pre-defined scores is used to select the most suitable foundation based on the soil and seabed conditions (Weller et al., 2015b). Gravity-based, pile, and suction caisson foundation options are available, and static and quasi-static analysis techniques are used to investigate the resistance to the applied loading for a given size and weight. Additional constraints are also used to limit the number of types selected for sites with varied seabed conditions (Weller et al., 2015b).

For floating devices, catenary and taut mooring systems are available and chosen to suit the tidal range and required position of the device within the water column. The choice of gravity-based, pile, direct-embedment, or drag-embedment anchor is then based on the type, depth, and layering of the soil as well as the predominant load direction (Weller et al., 2015b). Static and quasi-static analysis techniques are used to calculate the equilibrium floater position, mooring line pretension, and horizontal floater offsets due to steady wind, current, and mean wave drift loads. A simplified time-domain calculation can also be performed to estimate the motions and mooring line tensions due to both first-order wave excitation and second-order wave drift forces (Weller et al., 2015b). Options to share anchors and replace some length of chain with synthetic rope are included, and the module will iterate until the mooring system is deemed adequate in both ultimate (intact) and accidental (one line removed) limit states, and the loading and bending of the umbilical electrical cable are within the allowable limits (Weller et al., 2015b).

In practice, this tool is a 'black box' which reads in simplified descriptions of the device and local environment, considers design options which have been ranked and scored by scientific findings, empirical data, or 'best guess' estimates, and specifies the least expensive foundation or mooring system which meets the user requirements (DTOcean, 2015; Weller et al., 2015b). In the years since its launch, the DTOcean project has set the standard for open-source marine energy design tools. However, some users have found the tools both difficult to use without training and not sufficiently transparent as to how different design options are compared and selected (Noble & Medina-Lopez, 2018).

4.2. DTOceanPlus

A follow-up project, entitled DTOceanPlus (2018-2021), was later funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme to produce a second-generation suite of open-source marine energy design tools. In addition to updated versions of the previous design and assessment modules, the new tools include a stage gate module, which uses standard metrics to assess and guide the development of the technology, and a structured innovation module, which can generate new concepts and offer potential improvements (Nava et al., 2019a; 2019b). Further information on the DTOceanPlus tools, which are still in development, is available at: <http://dtoceanplus.eu/project-structure>.

In planning for the development of the second-generation design tools, the DTOceanPlus consortium used a webinar, web-based questionnaire, and focused interviews to consult with likely end users and gather feedback (Noble & Medina-Lopez, 2018). The users expected that they would primarily use these tools to assess how different devices would perform, either in isolation or within an array, at

different prospective sites and with different balances of plant (Noble & Medina-Lopez, 2018; Noble et al., 2018). The performance of the station-keeping system was viewed as the second most important array performance metric by the users, behind only power performance, and the ability to identify areas for cost reduction was viewed as the most important feature of the tool, above even the ability to maximise energy delivery (Noble & Medina-Lopez, 2018). Usability was identified as the most important consideration for the new design tools, followed by flexibility, expandability, and modularity. Transparency, particularly in linking assumptions and calculations to the underlying research, was another important consideration (Noble & Medina-Lopez, 2018; Noble et al., 2018). The users appeared less interested in the structured innovation module, as well as those related to the assessment of social and ecological impact (Noble & Medina-Lopez, 2018). The key requests for the second-generation design tool were greater usability and flexibility, the ability to run batch simulations to facilitate sensitivity studies, and the ability to connect with widely used analysis and design software packages (Noble & Medina-Lopez, 2018; Noble et al., 2018).

As with the previous version, the DTOceanPlus station-keeping module is not intended to provide detailed engineering design information but rather to facilitate initial assessments and support decision-making processes (Noble et al., 2018). The tool will be designed to enable different users (technology developers, project developers, public and private investors, etc.) to analyse different aspects of the development (components, devices, arrays), which may be at different technology readiness levels (concept definition, feasibility, design), with different levels of complexity (with the tool offering 'simple' and 'expert' modes) (Nava et al., 2019b; Noble et al., 2018). As before, the tool will be informed by data and methods obtained from scientific publications, industry best practices, and manufacturer's catalogues (Noble et al., 2018; Luxcey et al., 2020). The accuracy of the outputs will naturally depend on that of the inputs, but the new modules will be able to warn of unreliable data, identify system inefficiencies, and suggest potential solutions (Noble et al., 2018).

The station-keeping module will determine, as before, the most suitable anchor and foundation type based on the soil and seabed conditions, predominant load direction, and expected environmental impact (Luxcey et al., 2020). The size and weight of the anchor or foundation will then be adjusted to verify the design requirements regarding soil bearing capacities, anchor holding capacities, and foundation sliding and overturning resistances (Luxcey et al., 2020). The mooring analysis will be used to determine, as before, the equilibrium floater position, mooring line pretension, and horizontal floater offsets in both ultimate and accidental limit states.

The most significant updates to the station-keeping module will be the addition of frequency-domain dynamic analysis techniques to determine response amplitude operators and motion response power spectra for given devices and the expansion of the mooring design sub-module to include fatigue analysis, additional components such as clump weights, buoyancy modules, and master structures, and the production of input files for MAP++, an open-source, quasi-static mooring analysis programme (Luxcey et al., 2020). The new module will enable the user to perform foundation and mooring analyses in 'stand-alone' mode, which requires no connection to the other design tools, and will also be revised to reduce run times, increase accuracy, etc. (Noble et al., 2018; Luxcey et al., 2020).

In-house alpha testing of the DTOceanPlus station-keeping module is presently underway, and the beta version is expected to be released to the public in late 2021. Its developers have sought to provide additional features and greater functionality, but these upgrades will come with an additional challenge: to ensure that the new module is simpler to use, rather than more complicated, than the previous version.

4.3. MHKit

The Marine and Hydrokinetic Toolkit, MHKit, is a suite of open-source software tools and functions designed for the marine energy community. Developed as part of a collaboration between NREL, the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL), and Sandia National Laboratories (SNL), MHKit offers marine-energy-specific data-processing, analysis, and visualisation functions to supplement those provided by other software packages. Further information is available at: <https://mhkit-software.github.io/MHKit/>.

MHKit aims to provide a common development platform for the marine energy community, including standardised, referenced, and readable code bases, to enable the rapid processing of data obtained from numerical simulations, laboratory, and field measurements and assist with quality assurance and device certification studies. Its platform includes modules to calculate resource assessment and power performance metrics for wave (wave energy spectra, capture length matrices, annual energy production estimates, etc.) and tidal energy converters (principal flow directions, capture areas, exceedance probabilities, etc.), and tools to calculate mechanical loads and assess the quality of the power produced, as well as the quality of the data provided.

All calculations performed within MHKit are designed to adhere to the IEC 114 technical specifications for marine energy devices and follow best practices within the marine energy and offshore industries. The MHKit platform will also offer a dedicated mooring analysis module but this is not expected to be released until late 2021 and, as of yet, no details of its functionality have been made available.

4.4. OpenFAST

OpenFAST is an open-source, whole-system simulation tool for the design and analysis of onshore and offshore wind turbines. Developed by NREL and based on the earlier FAST v8 code, OpenFAST represents a transition to better support the open-source community in the use and further development of the various design and analysis modules within the FAST framework. Further information is available at: <https://www.nrel.gov/wind/nwtc/openfast.html>.

OpenFAST is primarily a wind turbine analysis tool, and so its modules are naturally less applicable to the design of foundations, moorings, and anchors for marine energy projects than those of DTOcean and DTOceanPlus. However, several OpenFAST modules may be relevant to marine energy design, including the BeamDyn and ElastoDyn structural dynamics modules; HydroDyn, which enables multiple approaches for calculating hydrodynamic loads; and SubDyn, which can be used to compute the mode shapes, natural frequencies, and time-domain responses of multi-member fixed substructures.

For mooring analysis, OpenFAST makes use of three open-source tools: FEAMooring, the finite-element-based mooring dynamics module developed by Texas A&M University; MAP++, the quasi-static mooring analysis module developed by NREL and the American Bureau of Shipping; and MoorDyn, the lumped-mass-based mooring dynamics module developed by the University of Maine. The dynamic mooring tools FEAMooring and MoorDyn were found to perform just as well as the equivalent commercial software, OrcaFlex, in predicting fairlead loads in wave tank validation studies, whilst the quasi-static mooring tool MAP++, which will also be used by the DTOceanPlus tool, was found to produce satisfactory agreement on mean loads and resulting platform motions (Wendt et al., 2016).

Each of the OpenFAST modules can be run either in stand-alone mode or within its suite of coupled aero-hydro-servo-elastic engineering models. The ability to run the modules in stand-alone mode offers an opportunity for users of the Selkie tools to export their results to OpenFAST for further analysis. Moreover, OpenFAST is packaged with many validated certification tests for offshore fixed and floating wind turbines which could be used as benchmark tests for new foundation, anchor, or mooring system designs. These opportunities will be explored further over the course of the project.

4.5. Comparison

The table below compares the key features of the tools described in the previous subsections.

Table 1: Key features of existing, open-source station-keeping tools.

Tool name	Station-keeping tool developer	Station-keeping design type	Station-keeping analysis type	Programming Language	External connections	Advantages	Disadvantages
DTOcean	University of Exeter	Static and quasi-static	Static and quasi-static	Python	Other DTOcean tools	First open-source station-keeping design tool; provides coupling with other array design tools and baseline level of knowledge to inform feasibility studies	Requires software download; difficult to use without training; not sufficiently transparent as to how design options are compared and selected
DTOceanPlus	France Energies Marines	Static and quasi-static; dynamic (frequency domain) for moorings only	Static and quasi-static; dynamic (frequency domain) for moorings only	Python	Other DTOceanPlus tools, MAP++	Extends capabilities of DTOcean tool; offers standalone mode and different complexity levels	To be confirmed
MHKit	NREL, PNNL, SNL	To be confirmed (for moorings only)	To be confirmed (for moorings only)	Python, MATLAB	To be confirmed	To be confirmed	To be confirmed
OpenFAST	NREL	Quasi-static and dynamic (time domain) for moorings only (via MAP++, FEAMooring, and MoorDyn)	Dynamic and coupled dynamic (time domain) for foundation and anchor loads, mooring loads and motions	Fortran	To be confirmed; potential to couple with various computational fluid dynamics tools	Whole-system design and analysis software; offers many validated certification tests	Focused on wind energy rather than marine energy; difficult to compare foundation designs; no capability to compare anchor designs

5. Discussion and conclusions

Foundations, anchors, and moorings have been identified as critical components for marine energy projects and key challenge areas for research and innovation. For marine energy devices, these systems not only provide station-keeping capabilities for high-value assets but can also influence, either directly or indirectly, the efficiency of the energy extraction. Because station-keeping systems also represent a significant proportion of the overall expenditure, the development of more efficient and bespoke systems will be crucial to the advancement of the marine energy industries. New designs, methods, and standards will be developed by the collaborative efforts of industry and academic stakeholders, and the sharing of information, via open-source models and publications, will ensure the continuous improvement of best practices.

Based on a review of the relevant literature and focused discussions with stakeholders from both Selkie and similar research projects, it is anticipated that the most useful form that a new, open-source foundation and mooring tool could take would be a web-based, decision-support tool designed to complement and expand on the station-keeping tools provided by the DTOcean and DTOceanPlus projects. As with these earlier projects, the objective for this new station-keeping tool would not be to eliminate the need for engineering knowledge and technical due diligence, but rather to provide a holistic view of all necessary design considerations and to facilitate the decision-making process at concept stage by enabling the rapid assessment and comparison of different design options and costs.

Similar to the existing DTOcean and proposed DTOceanPlus decision-support tools, the Selkie station-keeping tool should be able to produce, both quickly and simply, a preliminary design for a foundation, anchor, or mooring system based on the characteristics of the device and deployment site. It is proposed that the Selkie tool should also adopt an iterative design approach based on static and quasi-static analysis techniques and, as with the existing models, be developed with particular focus on usability, flexibility, and compatibility with other software packages. Unlike the DTOcean and DTOceanPlus tools, however, the Selkie tool will focus primarily on the Ireland-Wales region (the Irish and Celtic Seas) and be designed to assist developers in the earliest stages of device deployment: with a focus on pre-commercial demonstration projects rather than large arrays.

As with the geographic information systems (GIS) and techno-economic analysis tools being developed under work package 4 of the Selkie project (see O'Connell et al., 2021), it is proposed that the foundation and mooring tool should utilise a web-based platform and graphical user interface (GUI) to minimise user training requirements and facilitate frequent updates and improvements. The connection with these other Selkie tools will be a key asset for the new station-keeping tool: it is anticipated that the user will be able to browse an interactive map of the Ireland-Wales region, examine its collection of open-source metocean and theoretical wave and tidal stream energy resource datasets, and import data from a site of interest into the station-keeping tool. Once the basic information about the deployment site and proposed device has been established, the station-keeping tool will perform some simplified, computationally efficient calculations and return preliminary foundation, anchor, and mooring system designs, which can be used to compare different options and return the resulting costs to the logistics and techno-economic analysis tools. The station-keeping tool will be designed such that its outputs are easily visualised and compatible with other open-source and commercial analysis tools, where the user might continue their design work.

This framework for the station-keeping tool will be further developed in collaboration with project partners but also informed by surveys and focused discussions with prospective users. The first survey (the results of which are presented in an appendix to this report) and focused discussions have indicated strong support for this framework, suggesting that concept design, cost estimation, and

option studies would be the most useful aspects of design on which to focus (given that these are the phases traditionally performed in-house by project developers before outsourcing the data collection and detailed design phases) and emphasising the importance of usability and flexibility for prospective users. Given that the Selkie tool will be designed for the rapidly evolving marine energy industries, it will also be important to incorporate the latest techniques, components, and materials in station-keeping system design, and to provide sufficient transparency to enable the user to examine the research and assumptions underlying the design processes. The development of close links with the DTOcean and DTOceanPlus projects should ensure that the duplication of research and development effort is minimised and provide, for the marine energy community, the most efficient use of project resources.

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Appendix: Results of stakeholder survey

This appendix presents the results of an online survey which was designed to ensure that the Selkie foundation and mooring tool would be designed in line with the needs of the prospective users. The survey was first released at the stakeholder webinar on 26 November 2020, and remains available at the following link: <https://forms.gle/rxCm8C1yW3pVPFjS8>.

To date, only 10 responses have been recorded but the findings align well with those of the recent DTOceanPlus publications (see Noble et al., 2018; Noble & Medina-Lopez, 2018). The Selkie team supplemented the findings of this survey with 14 one-on-one interviews with industry and academic experts, and will continue to incorporate comments and suggestions received throughout the project.

Q1. In which type of industry are you involved?

10 responses

Q2. In which industries do you operate?

10 responses

Q3. Would you be willing to participate in a follow-up, one-on-one discussion to better inform our research?

10 responses

Q4. Are you currently, or have you been previously, involved in a wave or tidal stream energy pilot project?

10 responses

Q5. Please specify the device and station-keeping system type (e.g. floating wave device, catenary mooring system, gravity anchor) used in your pilot project.

6 responses

- Floating tidal 15kW
- Floating OWC catenary mooring
- OPERA and WavePiston: floating wave device, catenary mooring
- Floating wave and wind device with a taut mooring arrangement
- Catenary mooring
- Wave energy converter, catenary mooring system

Q6. What are the key lessons (regarding station-keeping systems) that you or your company learned from this pilot project?

6 responses

- At early design stage now.
- Design needs validation against tank testing
- The purpose of the mooring is not always only station keeping but also affects performance of energy system
- Difficult to obtain geotechnical information and anchor information to enable site screening and selection
- Floater dynamics are vastly different from our experience in oil & gas or maritime floaters
- How to implement the panels deflection in the mooring design

Q7. When (year), where (region, country), and at which scale (single device, multiple devices) do you hope to make your next deployment?

5 responses

- 2021 at META in Pembroke Dock
- 2021, USA, single pre commercial device
- Full scale (Wavepiston)
- 2023, TBC, full scale single device
- Not applicable

Q8. In your experience, what are the key design considerations for station-keeping systems?

10 responses

Q9. In your experience, what are the key design drivers for such systems?

10 responses

Q10. In your view, what will be the next important innovation in station-keeping system design?

10 responses

- Floating wind (I guess) and multiuse platforms
- Low cost installation systems
- Multi-array mooring systems, e.g. shared anchor points
- New anchor designs that avoid the use of major construction vessels

Q11. Which software tools do you use for foundation or anchor design?

10 responses

Q12. Which software tools do you use for mooring system design?

10 responses

Q13. Which standards do you use for station-keeping design?

10 responses

Q14. Station-keeping systems are presently designed for an operational life of 25 years. How do you view this design life?

10 responses

Q15. In your experience, which aspects of station-keeping system design are most likely to be done in-house?

10 responses

Q16. In your experience, which aspects are most likely to be outsourced?

10 responses

Q17. Does your design process involve open source software (OpenFAST, MoorDyn, etc.)? If yes, please specify which and for what purpose. If no, please explain why not.

4 responses

- Wec-Sim
- I'm studying anchor design
- Third party lead.
- WEC-Sim for device hydrodynamic simulation incl. mooring loads

Q18. In which areas do you think a station-keeping system decision-support tool could be most helpful?

9 responses

Q19. In your view, which attributes would be most important for such a tool?

10 responses

Q20. Do you use the decision-support tools provided by the DTOcean project? If yes, please specify which and for what purpose. If no, please explain why.

5 responses

- No, too early in the design process now.
- Not yet, time required to get up to speed with software is prohibitive
- No, we use GM OpSim
- No, not aware of it
- No, we use GM OpSim

Q21. If you have used the DTOcean tools, which aspects did you find most useful?

8 responses

Q22. If you have used the DTOcean tools, which aspects did you find least useful?

8 responses

Q23. Please provide any additional comments, thoughts, or suggestions that you feel may be relevant to our research.

1 response

- Mooring systems can provide stability as well as station keeping (TLP/Gravity bases). The planned software may be able to consider that aspect as well.